

FEAR OF MISSING OUT AND PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS: THE MEDIATING ROLES OF PROBLEMATIC SOCIAL MEDIA USE AND SOCIAL COMPARISON

Tayyeb Ramazan¹, Sundus Rafi², Muhammad Farrukh³, Nadeem Idris⁴

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Corresponding Author: *

Tayyeb Ramazan

Abstract

The rapid growth of social media has changed how people interact with each other, but has also caused some fears about its effects on mental health. A psychological construct that has become increasingly popular in the given context is the fear of missing out (FOMO), a state of anxiety about being left out of pleasurable social experiences. This paper has explored the connections among FOMO, problematic social media use (PSMU), social comparison and psychological well-being with specific emphasis on depression and anxiety. The study design employed a cross-sectional survey, and data were collected through standardised self-report measures, which included 428 active social media users in Pakistan in October and December 2023. The proposed model was tested by means of regression and mediation analysis. The results found that FOMO was a significant predictor of depression, anxiety, problematic use of social media, and social comparison. Another finding was that problematic social media use and social comparison had a strong connection with increased depression and anxiety levels. According to the mediation analyses, both independently and in series, PSMU and social comparison mediated the relationships between FOMO and psychological distress. These findings indicate that FOMO plays a role in mental health issues not only directly but indirectly due to excessive use of social media and increased social comparison. The paper emphasizes the need to consider FOMO-relevant cognitions and unhealthy behaviors of social media when trying to enhance psychological well-being. Promotion of better digital habits and dependence on online validation could be used to curb depression and anxiety in social media users.

INTRODUCTION

The rapid adoption of internet technologies has significantly altered all communication patterns, interactions, and information consumption. Of these technologies, social media platforms have found their way into the heart of everyday life, and some people are now in constant communication, regardless of geographical borders. Although these sites provide opportunities to communicate, express oneself and be socially supported, there is increasing evidence that there are severe psychological and behavioural outcomes of excessive and maladaptive social media use. The fear of missing out (FOMO) is one of the phenomena which has attracted a considerable

amount of scholarly attention in this context. Fear of missing out is usually characterized as a universal fear that other people might be having some meaningful activities that one is not part of, and the urge to stay in constant contact with what other people are doing (Przybylski et al., 2013). The fear of social exclusion is not a recent development due to the advent of digital technologies; the emergence of social media has made it more pronounced and acceptable, as people are subjected to the constant presence of the actions, successes and socializing efforts of other individuals. Consequently, FOMO has become highly common during the digital era, especially among young adults

who use social networking sites as a significant source of social interaction and identity formation.

Problematic social media usage (PSMU), or excessive, compulsive, and maladaptive social media use, is closely linked to the development of FOMO and has been identified as disruptive to the daily functioning and well-being of end users. PSMU is defined by the lack of control over use, constant obsession with social networking sites, and the inability to stop using negative effects (Elhai et al., 2019). Patients with PSMU tend to respond with the use of too much time and mental resources on the Internet, sacrificing their academic performance, job performance, interpersonal relationships, and mental well-being. Numerous studies have so far identified PSMU as a risk factor associated with poor mental health, such as more symptoms of depression, anxiety, stress, and lower life satisfaction (Elhai et al., 2018; Wolniewicz and Elhai, 2021). Though certain studies highlight the possible advantages of using social media, e.g. increased perceived social support and self-expression, they seem to fade away as the usage becomes too heavy or compulsive. Under these circumstances, the use of social media can contribute to emotional distress instead of relieving it (Sagioglou & Greitemeyer, 2014).

Constant social comparison is one of the mechanisms according to which PSMU can have a detrimental impact on psychological well-being. The appearance of social media often embodies a perfect image of the lives of other people, and, in this case, it may promote social comparison and inadequacy. The studies show that those who spend a lot of time social comparing on social media claim lower self-esteem, negative affectivity, and poor well-being, overall (Tiamiyu & Elhai, 2019). To much association with social media also effects thair real life identity (Farrukhet al., 2023) Notably, FOMO has been identified to exacerbate social comparison inclinations, hence, strengthening maladaptive engagement patterns and emotional suffering. Although the academic interest in PSMU has been rising, a good portion of the research work has been more concentrated on affective consequences, including positive and negative feelings, as opposed to looking at wider psychological and cognitive processes. Indicatively, in most studies, they have been based on general measures of affect, which might not be of clinical

interest. Conversely, there is a gap in the number of studies investigating the role of cognitive processes in influencing the onset and continuation of problematic social media patterns, including rumination and attentional bias. New evidence implies that rumination has a positive correlation with PSMU severity, as it can be suggested that maladaptive thinking styles can be the key to maintaining excessively engaging (Elhai & Weeks, 2018).

FOMO has also been found to be one of the core psychological issues contributing to the connection between social media use and mental health outcomes. According to longitudinal and mediation studies, FOMO mediates the correlation between PSMU and depression and anxiety symptoms (Wolniewicz & Elhai, 2021). These results suggest that people with a higher level of FOMO are especially susceptible to the development of harmful social media consumption patterns, which, in turn, will worsen psychological discomfort. Nevertheless, it is not entirely clear in which direction this relationship is directed, since excessive use of social media could also contribute to the development of FOMO, as it makes people more exposed to the lives and activities of other people. It directly effects their social bonding and deteriorates their cognitive process (Farrukh et al., 2022). The theoretical frameworks of self-determination theory and the limited capacity model help to shed much light on these dynamics. The self-determination theory states that relatedness (desire to establish a connection with other individuals) is one of the basic psychological needs that are necessary to operate optimally (Ryan & Deci, 2017). In case people lack adequate social contact in the offline space, they can resort to social media to address the lack of relationships. Nevertheless, overdependence on Internet communication can backfire, making the social connection in the real world less strong and more susceptible to FOMO and mental health disorders.

The same can be said of the limited capacity model which assumes that individuals have limited cognitive capacity to process information. Overexposure to digital material can overwhelm such resources, resulting in attentional exhaustion, emotional dysregulation, and lack of self-control. In this light, problematic social media users might have a cognitive

overload, lack commitment to offline relationships and grow more reliant on digital communication to control emotions, which increases FOMO. The two opposing sides of the literature on the co-relationship of FOMO and PSMU prevail. According to the former, problematic use of social media is among the factors that lead to FOMO. In this perspective, overuse of social media exposes other people and their activities, worsens social comparison and strengthens fears of being excluded. This view is supported by empirical research, which found that people with more PSMU also have more FOMO and suffer emotionally (Steers & Acitelli, 2014).

The second view is that FOMO is the antecedent of problematic social media use and a cause. Those having fears of not being able to share social experiences might feel the need to obsessively keep track of the social networking sites to keep abreast of the latest happenings and socialize with others. Gradually, it can develop into maladaptive patterns of use that can be described as compulsive checking and emotional dependence (Elhai et al., 2018). In spite of the empirical evidence on both sides of the argument, the bulk of the existing research has been based on a cross-sectional design, which curtails the findings on causation and mutual impact. Recent studies have started focusing on the significance of studying such relationships over time. Longitudinal designs will be able to evaluate both directional effects of FOMO and PSMU on each other over the period, which will provide deeper insight into the dynamic interaction between them. Nonetheless, these studies are limited, especially among the student population of the university, which is one of the most active users of social media sites.

The youth of university students is one of the most vulnerable cohorts because of the developmental issues of the onset of adulthood. The given life phase is defined by the exploration of identities, a high level of attention to evaluation by peers, and more significant dependence on online communication. The ever-present connectivity that social media provides can escalate FOMO and promote the use of maladaptive engagement patterns, which can negatively affect a person psychologically and in academics. Another important variable in the relationships between FOMO, PSMU and mental health is social support. According to recent research,

social support in real life could be the mediator between problematic use of social media and psychological health (Lin et al., 2022). In particular, augmented PSMU is connected to weaker social support offline, which in turn forecasts worse mental health outcomes. Nevertheless, scanty studies have differentiated between offline and online social support as part of this framework, which underscores a need to conduct more research. To address these gaps, the given study will be designed to investigate the two-way interaction between the fear of missing out and harmful social media use based on the longitudinal design. Also, this paper explores the importance of social comparison and psychological well-being in this framework, offering a combined view of how the processes of excessive social media use work. Targeting university students, the study contributes to a more complex interpretation of digital behavior in a crucial stage of development and informs the interventions that will help in maintaining healthier and more balanced social media consumption.

One has found out that a person who has a high degree of fear of missing out is deemed to have a strong urge to always. Keep pace or get to know what other people are doing on social media. One of the prior studies has reported that when one feels the fear of missing out, they might seek to reduce their state of anxiety by keeping track of the actions of other people via social media (Van Rooij et al., 2018). Moreover, fear of missing out seems to be more widespread among the participants when they cannot access (Mannion & Nolan, 2020). Nonetheless, the more people log into their social networking platforms, the more they understand that they are not experiencing different events. This vicious circle can, in turn, perpetuate itself, resulting in other psychological symptoms. There is a tendency of social comparison through social media platforms where people compare their lives against those of others through online portrayals. Such a comparison makes FOMO worse because users feel that their lives are not as good as the seemingly better experience of others (Fistingier & Alt, 2019). They noted that the degree of FOMO was highly correlated with the degree of social media use prompted by the desire to overcome the feelings of inferiority caused by social media comparison.

A great number of studies have also created a significant correlation between FOMO and the expanded consumption of social media. (Przybylski et al., 2013) established that the more people are afraid of missing out (FOMO), the more time they spend on social media. (Przybylski et al., 2013) also found that FOMO cause symptoms of internet communication disorder, bringing about excessive online consumption. The social comparison has an interaction with social media use and FOMO that greatly affects the well-being of an individual. According to Elhai et al. (2018), frequent social media users were found to have a higher level of anxiety, depression, and less life fulfilment when the researchers documented the relation between FOMO and these conditions. This association between the use of social media as a result of FOMO and social comparison and the reduced well-being highlights the negative impact of social media overuse on mental health.

The term social anxiety signifies the distress or nervousness that people feel when they are in social interaction or even in social surroundings that involve interactions between people. The causes of this could be negative criticism of other people, emotional pressure, pain, self-awareness, anxiety, or anxieties of social life. Consequently, people can decide to separate themselves from the real world to escape possible negative appraisals. Some studies have also established a relationship between social anxiety and the behaviours of people in problematic social media use (Alkis et al., 2017). The extent to which depression has been positively correlated with excessive social media use has become an increasingly popular issue, with studies showing that people who exhibit dangerous behaviors about social media consumption, including spending too much time, relentless self-comparison with others, are more likely to experience depressive symptoms. There are several studies which have explored this relationship. A major correlation was discovered between depression among young adults and excessive use of social media (Primack et al., 2017). Another study (Twenge & Campbell, 2018) also found a time-related relationship between the development of social media and the increase in depression and suicidal ideation among teenagers. Moreover, a meta-analysis of (Primack et al., 2017) involved several studies and

proved that there is a high correlation between problematic use of social media and depression. The unending exposure to well-edited and idealised portrayals of the lives of others on social media platforms can lead to a sense of inferiority and self-worth issues and eventually develop depressive tendencies.

Social comparison and depression have been regarded as highly researched and therefore, shed some light on how comparing oneself against others influences the level of mental well-being. In social comparison theory, people evaluate their own social person value based on their comparison with other people on different facets. Such comparisons, especially in the case of social image, can assist in the occurrence and intensification of depressive symptoms. A study that was carried out by Smith and Kim (2007) revealed that frequent and unfavourable social comparisons are associated with increased perceptions of depression. Those who are involved in upward social comparison, that is, seeing other people as more successful or in better situations, can feel inadequate and have low self-esteem, thus adding to the depressive tendencies. The correlation between social comparison and anxiety is a psychological topic that has received a lot of research. Studies have also revealed that people who often find themselves in the habit of unfavourable social comparisons have higher chances of developing anxiety. The social comparison theory states that individuals tend to assess their abilities, opinions, and attributes in comparison to others. When the outcomes of these comparisons cause inadequacies or fall short, it may cause increased levels of anxiety.

The research held by Buunk and Gibbons (2007) established that the use of social comparison as a source of self-evaluation can result in anxiety in a person when they feel that they are inferior to others. This helps in the idea that upward social comparison, where one compares oneself to that individual who they think is more successful or competent, is especially anxiety-inducing. Moreover, social comparison through social media can also be a cause of anxiety. Such platforms usually show filters and perfect images of people's lives of people. Continuous presence of seemingly ideal lives and the success of other people on platforms such as Instagram or Facebook can make unrealistic demands and

exacerbate the feeling of social anxiety. Currently, the rising occurrence of mental illnesses among the youth is a major international community health concern. In Malaysia, it is identified that the highest percentage is attributed to persons over the age of 20 years and above in terms of mental health disorders. According to the National Mental Health and Morbidity Survey, 36.6% and 79.45 were found to be the prevalence of depression and anxiety among the youth.

The research carried out by health sciences students of the International Islamic University Malaysia (IIUM) demonstrated that out of 102 participants, over one-third of the respondents reported feeling depression, which is in line with the results obtained by Nahas et al. (2019). Equally, an earlier study conducted in Malaysia found that there is a strong correlation between internet addiction and depression (Osman et al., 2017). These findings taken together suggest the urgent need to develop effective preventive and intervention programs due to the severity of mental health issues in young people.

Even though current studies have identified the links between fear of missing out (FOMO), problematic social media use (PSMU), social comparison, and mental health outcomes, including depression and anxiety, scarce studies have been conducted on specific populations in Malaysia. This lapse is especially noticeable in the case of university students since most empirical research has been carried out in a Western background. The students of health sciences are a particularly vulnerable population because of the educational requirements and the psychological pressure within complicated learning conditions (Nahas et al., 2019). Studies on FOMO have found mild to moderate correlations between FOMO and symptoms of depression and anxiety in cross-cultural research in the United States (Wolniewicz & Elhai, 2020), Turkey (Gul et al., 2019), and South Korea (Kim & Koh, 2018). These results indicate that FOMO and PSMU, as well as social comparison, can be the causal factors of the emergence of psychopathology (Dewald-Kaufmann & Grob, 2015).

FOMO and psychological well-being can be further explained by the social comparison processes and problematic social media use. According to the theory of uses and gratifications, people use the media to satisfy their psychological needs, such as self-

evaluation and social validation. In this context, FOMO could exacerbate the social comparative processes, which can cause more psychological distress (Gibbons & Buunk, 2019). People who express a higher level of uncertainty of self-concept and are more sensitive to behavior of others are highly likely to make social comparisons (Campbell et al., 1996; Gibbons & Buunk, 1999). It is also possible to analyze the connection between social comparison orientation (SCO) and PSMU in terms of FOMO because FOMO is, in its essence, conditioned by the comparative analysis of the experiences that one goes through in comparison with those of others (Shen & Liu, 2020). FOMO is a phenomenon according to the self-determination theory (SDT), which occurs when fundamental psychological needs, such as competence, autonomy, and relatedness, are fulfilled (or not fulfilled) temporarily or chronically (Deci & Ryan, 2010). Studies on behavioral addiction and videogame conditions have shown that these fundamental needs are closely related to adaptive self-regulation and mental health (Przybylski & Weinstein, 2013).

FOMO has been operationalized as the fear of missing out on rewarding social activity, the reason why people are compelled to stay constantly in touch with their social networks (Przybylski et al., 2013). It has also been associated with the need-to-belong theory that suggests that people who are more interested in belonging to a group are more vulnerable to FOMO (Alutaybi & Ali, 2020). This can result in people spending more time on social networking sites just to prevent the feeling of being excluded, which can then transition to obsessive use of the internet and smartphones (Jin et al., 2020). The previous research has consistently confirmed direct and indirect correlations of FOMO with problematic smartphone use (Elhai & Montak, 2020; Wang et al., 2019). Moreover, FOMO has been identified to be predicted by social comparison orientation in such a way that often, people who often compare themselves with others tend to rate their experience negatively and thus, become envious and dissatisfied (Reer et al., 2019; Reer & Quandt, 2019). Despite the studies done concerning FOMO and self-concept, there are only a few studies done on self-concept. Having consistent and consistent self-concepts also makes people feel less uncertain in social situations, which

could counter FOMO. In contrast, people who have weak self-concepts can use social networking sites more actively to find confirmation and escape the sense of social rejection (Hassan et al., 2023; Alutaybi et al., 2020). These trends have been determined to be predictors of compulsive internet behavior and problematic socialization (Jin et al., 2020).

The empirical research evidence has shown that high FOMO correlates with adverse psychological and physiological effects. Nevertheless, the connection between FOMO and social media fatigue is under-researched, even though there is evidence that high FOMO individuals are more engaged and compulsive users of social media (Wolniewicz et al., 2018). Overuse and monotony of social media can contribute to an increase in social comparison, depression, and anxiety, and thus, adversely affect the psychological well-being (Karapanos et al., 2016). Several studies have investigated antecedents of FOMO, such as interpersonal concerns, depressive symptoms, and personality traits. The consequences of FOMO identified include switching to other platforms, temporary withdrawal from social media, disengagement, and full abandonment of social media (Lee et al., 2014). Social media fatigue has also been linked with less life satisfaction, lower productivity, and worsening mental and physical health. Although these results have been reached, the connection between FOMO and psychological well-being has not been studied thoroughly. In this regard, the current research will examine the correlations between FOMO and PSMU, social comparison, anxiety, and depression (Shin & Shin, 2016).

Problematic social media usage means excessive and uncontrolled social network service use, which is similar to behavioral dependency and disrupts normal functioning (Andreassen et al., 2021). Even though social media helps to exchange information and be socially connected (Carlson et al., 2016; Savcı et al., 2020), pathological use has been associated with negative health impacts both physically and mentally (Butt & Hassan, 2024; Kuss & Griffiths, 2017). In previous studies, PSMU has been linked to interpersonal problems, occupational inability, sleep problems, depression, anxiety, and low levels of life satisfaction (Blachnio et al., 2016; Keel et al., 2020; Liu and Ma, 2020; Müller et al., 2016; Szczygiel and Podwalski, 2020; Zivnuska et al., 2020). As a result,

the interest in finding psychosocial mechanisms that underlie PSMU and their consequences on clinical intervention increases (Sun & Zhang, 2021). The attachment theory also provides a useful approach to FOMO and PSMU. This has been theorized as a type of addiction disorder, in which the insecure attachment styles predispose one to dysfunctional coping styles (Flores, 2022; Hassan et al., 2022). Adult attachment has been demonstrated to have an impact on well-being and proneness to addiction-related behaviors (Bartholomew et al., 2019; Gori et al., 2022). It has been proposed that secure attachment has a positive relationship with life satisfaction and negative relationship with PSMU, and anxious and avoidant attachment patterns are characterized by greater FOMO and problematic digital behaviors (Darienzo et al., 2019; Stovold & Herzberg, 2021).

The uses and gratification theory (UGT) can be applied to the use of electronic media including the use of smartphones. According to UGT, there are certain needs that individuals will want to satisfy with the help of mass media due to their peculiarities. In addition, such needs would make people use a specific kind of media to fulfill such needs (Blumer et al., 2022; Ali & Hassan, 2016). UGT considers both individual characteristics, psychological and psychopathological characteristics. Recent literature has affirmed the concept how the problematic social media use (PSMU) can be explained by individual difference as UGT (Park, 2023). People having high fear of missing out need to strive to satisfy their social self esteem by using social media platforms, including smartphones, more frequently. Whiting and Williams (2013) argue. The Uses and gratification theory is a communication theory that provides the reason why people select given media due to their needs and desires. This demonstrates that individuals are seeking means of getting to know each other and fulfilling their demands. This theory is applicable in the social media sector, where one would want to understand why people use social platforms and how they find satisfaction in its use.

Whiting and Williams (2013) also concluded that social media can play a vital role in the development of better scales and measures that marketers can utilize. The underlying principle of the theory of uses and gratification is that the people want to find ways of satisfying their needs which will eventually result

into gratification. Despite its specific applicability to the case of social media, the given theory has not been adequately addressed in the literature on marketing and social media. This paper seeks to apply the theory of uses and gratification in providing an effective and comprehensive insight into the motivations of the users towards using social media. As it has its origins in communications literature, the theory can be applied and used in the social media domain. Social media is the medium of communication that allows consumers or communicate with an unlimited number of people across the entire world potentially to billions of people (Williams et al., 2012). The very idea of the uses and gratification theory assumes that people actively pursue someone or something, usually

among the rival employees, to gratify their needs and to eventually be satisfied. (Lariscy et al., 2011). Despite the fact that used and gratification theory is commonly applied to other fields, it has the potential to be applied to the social media usage. The theory of uses and gratification gives an understanding of why individuals are addicted to social media. Theoretically individuals use social media to meet their needs and wants of satisfying their social interaction, entertainment and relaxation needs. Nonetheless, overreliance on social media by people to meet their needs might result into addictive behaviors. As a result, the theory of uses and gratification will be useful in understanding the motivations behind social media addiction (Whiting and Williams, 2013).

Methodology

The research design used in this study was the cross-sectional survey design that was used to investigate the relationships between fear of missing out (FOMO), problematic social media use (PSMU), social comparison, depression, and anxiety. An online self-administered questionnaire was used to collect data between October and December 2023. The 429 participants were initially recruited via simple random sampling that was probability based which saw 428 respondents holding up valid responses in the final analysis. I chose the cross-sectional design because it is cost-effective, more time-saving, and could be used to determine relations between two or more

psychological variables at one point in time (Setia, 2016). The use of questionnaires is especially useful when targeting large and diverse groups of people and to analyze the relationships between predictors and outcomes (Wang and Cheng, 2020). There were 45 questions of the survey, comprising of FOMO (9), PSMU (10), depression (7), anxiety (7), and social comparison (10) measures. The target population was represented by active users of social media who lived in Pakistan and they represented various age groups, gender and residential backgrounds (urban, suburban and rural). Simple random sampling was used in selection so that every individual had equal chances of being selected and therefore, high representativeness and low sampling bias was achieved (Cochran, 1977; Salkind, 2010). It was found that the final sample size

was sufficient to perform statistical analysis and be able to generalize it to the whole population of social media users (Creswell, 2014; Johnson & Christensen, 2019). Within this study, five variables have been identified. Encompassing the independent variable Fear of missing out, the dependent variable's, depression+anxiety, the mediator variable Problematic social media usage, and the moderator variable of social comparison.

Fear of missing out is measure by 10 items on a Likert scale from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree often. Which includes, "I fear others have more rewarding experiences than me." "I fear my friends have more rewarding experiences than me." "I get worried when I find out my friends are having fun without me." "I get anxious when I don't know what my friends are up to." "It is important that I understand my friends "in jokes". Sometimes, I wonder if I spend too much time keeping up with what is going on." "It bothers me when I miss an opportunity to meet up with friends." "When I have a good time it is important for me to share the details online (e.g. updating status)." "When I miss out on a planned get-to gather it bothers me." "When I go on vacation, I continue to keep tabs on what my friends are doing." This scale is referred to (Przybylski & Gladwell, 2013) motivational, emotional and behavioral correlates of fear of missing out. Problematic social media usage is measured by 10 on Likert scale of 1=Strongly disagree and 5=Strongly agree for assessing PSMU. The scale is developed by (Kwon & Yang, 2013). Depression and anxiety both are measured by 7,7 items of scale and that, scale is

developed by (Lovibond, 1983). Social comparison variable is measured by 11 Likert scale of items 1= Strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree. The scale is developed by Gibbons and Buunk (2019).

Analysis

Table 1 shows the demographic features of 428 respondents that participated in the study. The gender distributions were generally equal as there were 52.3 male and 47.7 female participants, which is a sufficient representation of genders. In terms of regional background, the highest percentage of respondents (39.3) lived in urban regions, secondly, there were those in rural (35.5) and suburban regions (25.2) implying that there was a good geographic representation of Pakistan. With regards to occupation, most of the respondents were occupied (59.6%), and housewives made up 23.4% of respondents. The proportion of students was 9.3 and 5.1% were not working, which shows that the sample mainly consisted of economically active people. The percentage of individuals in other classes was very low (0.2). In terms of monthly payments, almost half of the respondents (45.3) said that they earned 200,000 PKR or more, which means that the sample consists of a relatively high-income population. Moreover, 24.8% of them earned 100,000-150,000 PKR, and 20.1% earned 50,000-100,000 PKR. The low-income groups were underrepresented. In general, the income distribution indicates that a significant percentage of the participants were in middle- and high-income groups.

Table 1: Demographics

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Cumulative %
Gender	Male	224	52.3	52.3
	Female	204	47.7	100
Region	Rural	152	35.5	35.5
	Suburban	108	25.2	60.7
	Urban	168	39.3	100
Occupation	Employed	255	59.6	59.6
	Housewife	100	23.4	83
	Student	40	9.3	92.3
	Unemployed	22	5.1	97.4

Monthly Income	Other	1	0.2	100
	Below 50k	5	1.2	1.2
	50k-60k	2	0.5	1.7
	50k-100k	86	20.1	21.8
	100k-150k	106	24.8	46.6
	150k-200k	35	8.2	54.8
	200k or more	194	45.3	100

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Alpha	Items
FOMO	428	3.54	1.23	0.95	10
PSMU	428	3.59	1.21	0.95	10
Depression	428	3.00	0.94	0.92	7
Anxiety	428	2.94	0.95	0.92	7
Social Comparison	428	3.54	1.18	0.94	11

Table 2 shows that fear of missing out has 10 items, with an alpha value 0.95, a mean 3.54 and SD 1.23. Problematic social media usage has 10 items with an alpha value 0.95, SD 1.21 and mean 3.59. Depression has 7 items with an alpha value 0.92, a mean 3.00 and SD 0.94. Anxiety has 7 items with an alpha value 0.92, SD 0.95 and Mean 2.94. Social comparison with 11 items with an alpha value 0.94, SD 1.18 and a mean 3.54.

Table 3 shows the regression analysis of the connections between the fear of missing out (FOMO), problematic social media use (PSMU), social comparison, depression, and anxiety. The findings suggest that all the relationships suggested are statistically significant and positive with strong correlations between the two key variables. FOMO was also a strong predictor of various outcomes. In particular, FOMO was a strong predictor of depression ($R^2 = 0.60$, $B = 0.58$) and anxiety ($R^2 = 0.50$, $B = 0.51$), which indicated that more individuals with a higher degree of FOMO are likely to report a high level of psychological distress. FOMO was also significantly affecting problematic social media use ($R^2 = 0.70$, $B = 0.83$), which demonstrates that fear of missing out is a significant contributor to excessive and compulsive use of social media websites. Also,

FOMO was an important predictor of social comparison ($R^2 = 0.60$, $B = 0.74$), indicating the role of FOMO in exacerbating comparative behaviors online.

Social media use was also found to be a strong predictor of mental health outcomes, especially problematic social media use. More PSMU was also correlated with more depression ($R^2 = 0.60$, $B = 0.60$) and anxiety ($R^2 = 0.50$, $B = 0.59$), which shows that overindulgence in social media is worse off in terms of psychological well-being. Further, PSMU was an important predictor of social comparison ($R^2 = 0.60$, $B = 0.76$), indicating that the higher the exposure to social media content, the stronger the social comparison inclination among people. Social comparison itself was a good predictor of psychological distress, and had strong effects on both depression ($R^2 = 0.50$, $B = 0.60$) and anxiety ($R^2 = 0.60$, $B = 0.63$). All in all, these results indicate a vicious cycle where FOMO enhances problematic social media use and social comparison, which in turn leads to more depression and anxiety, which provides very strong empirical evidence for the proposed model.

Table 3: Regression Analysis

Relation	Rsqr	B	SE	T	Sig
FOMO->Dep	0.6	0.58	0.024	23.98	Significant
FOMO->Anxiety	0.5	0.51	0.025	22.39	Significant
FOMO->PSMU	0.7	0.83	0.022	33.19	Significant
FOMO->SC	0.6	0.74	0.030	24.97	Significant
PSMU->Dep	0.6	0.60	0.025	23.51	Significant
PSMU->Anxiety	0.5	0.59	0.026	22.88	Significant
PSMU->SC	0.6	0.76	0.030	25.44	Significant
SC->Dep	0.5	0.60	0.020	22.91	Significant
SC->Anxiety	0.6	0.63	0.025	25.34	Significant

The findings that are identified in the indirect effects table indicate that problematic social media use (PSMU) and social comparison (SC) are powerful mediating factors in the association between fear of missing out (FOMO) and psychological distress, which in this case is depression and anxiety. The indirect effects and the confidence intervals were not equal to zero, and this showed that all the indirect paths were statistically significant and thus there were significant mediation effects. The results are always in the form of partial mediation that is, FOMO has a direct and indirect impact on depression and anxiety via mediating variables.

More specifically, there was a partial mediation of the relationship between FOMO and depression and FOMO and anxiety by PSMU. It shows that the more people have FOMO, the more they are prone to excessive and compulsive usage of social media, which in its turn predisposes them to more depressive and anxiety symptoms. In the same way, social comparison was a significant mediator on its own in the interactions between FOMO and depression, as well as anxiety. These findings indicate that FOMO increases the propensity of individuals towards self-comparison with other people, especially on social networks, which in its turn worsens emotional distress. Additionally, the sequential mediation analyses give a more in-depth understanding of how

the underlying mechanism works since the process illustrates that FOMO influences depression and anxiety in a chain process, considering both PSMU and social comparison. FOMO promotes problematic use of social media in these models, which causes more social comparison, which then results in more depression and anxiety. Though the indirect effects in the sequential models were not as significant as the ones realized in the single-mediator models, nonetheless they were significant, which speaks to the cumulative effects of maladaptive digital actions and cognitive comparison processes on mental health.

Overall, these results can indicate that FOMO is one of the core psychological motivators to start a sequence of actions and thoughts, i.e., excessive use of social media and increased social comparison, which leads to the emergence of psychological distress. The similarity in the pattern of partial mediation in all models implies that depressive and anxiety outcomes might be directly affected by FOMO, but the outcomes are significantly enhanced by these mediating factors. This shows the significance of focusing not only on FOMO itself but also on problematic social media activities and social comparison tendencies when developing interventions that would lead to a decrease in anxiety and depression rates among social media users.

Table 4: Mediation Analysis

Indirect Relationship	Total Effect (β)	Direct Effect (β)	Indirect Effect (β)	95% Confidence Interval (Lower-Upper)	Conclusion
FOMO → PSMU → Depression	0.5816***	0.3296***	0.2520***	0.1416 - 0.3719	Partial Mediation
FOMO → PSMU → Anxiety	0.5700***	0.2910***	0.2800***	0.1750 - 0.3719	Partial Mediation
FOMO → SC → Anxiety	0.5700***	0.2630***	0.3100***	0.2300 - 0.3900	Partial Mediation
FOMO → SC → Depression	0.5816***	0.3504***	0.2312***	0.1554 - 0.3134	Partial Mediation
FOMO → PSMU → SC → Depression	0.5816***	0.2325***	0.0900***	0.0300 - 0.0500	Partial Mediation
FOMO → PSMU → SC → Anxiety	0.5700***	0.1530***	0.1300***	0.1000 - 0.2500	Partial Mediation

Discussion

The current research observed how fear of missing out (FOMO), problematic social media use (PSMU), social comparison, and psychological well-being correlate with each other with a specific reference to social media users in Pakistan in terms of depression and anxiety. The results of the study are highly empirical evidence of the suggested model and add to the body of literature that proves FOMO is a key psychological antecedent of an unfavorable digital behavior and mental health outcomes. In line with the existing studies, FOMO has been discovered to be a powerful and significant indicator of depression and anxiety. Those who feel more worried about the lack of rewarding social life experiences expressed increased levels of psychological distress, which confirms the previous results that FOMO is strongly linked to depressive symptoms, anxiety, and stress (Przybylski et al., 2013; Elhai et al., 2018; Wolniewicz & Elhai, 2020). These findings point to the fact that constant anxiety about social rejection and perceived insufficiency can disrupt emotional control and health, especially in digitally overloaded settings. The findings also revealed that FOMO highly predicts problematic social media use and thus, the high-FOMO people are likely to have excessive, compulsive and uncontrolled social media use. This observation is consistent with the uses and gratifications theory, which explains that human beings are active

consumers of media to gratify their psychological needs that are not met (belongness, self-esteem, and social validation) (Katz et al., 1974; Whiting and Williams, 2013). In case these needs are not met properly on the offline platform, people might turn to social media more and more often, which might develop into a dangerous use pattern (Elhai & Montak, 2020).

It was also observed that problematic use of social media is a significant predictor of both anxiety and depression, which supports the fact that excessive use of social media platforms can adversely influence mental health. The same results have been observed in the previous literature that PSMU is connected with emotional exhaustion, lower levels of life satisfaction, depression, and anxiety (Kuss & Griffiths, 2017; Keel et al., 2020; Liu & Ma, 2020). The current evidence implies that as much as social media can be used to connect, overdependence on social media can result in being exposed to adverse social judgment, information overload, and emotional exhaustion, hence leading to psychological distress.

Another important mechanism that the relationship between FOMO, PSMU and mental health outcomes has been found in the social comparison. The findings demonstrated that both FOMO and PSMU significantly forecasted social comparison, which then forecasted amplified cases of depression and anxiety.

The findings are in line with the social comparison theory, which believes that when comparing themselves with others, individuals measure their self-worth by doing the upward comparison; in most cases, resulting in negative self-evaluation when the upward comparisons are preponderant (Festinger, 1954; Buunk & Gibbons, 2007). This is magnified by social media sites, which show idealistic and edited images of the lives of other people, raising the chances of making negative comparisons and emotional pain (Tiamiyu & Elhai, 2019).

Notably, the mediation analyses offered a deeper understanding of the psychological processes that were happening. The findings showed that both PSMU and social comparison partially mediate the relationship between FOMO and depression as well as anxiety. This implies that FOMO not only has a direct impact on mental health but also an indirect effect through the overuse of social media and increased levels of social comparison. These results align with the past examination of literature indicating that FOMO is a cognitive-emotional weakness that prompts deviant online conduct, which consequently intensifies psychological symptoms (Wang et al., 2019; Reer et al., 2019). Besides, the sequential mediation outcome indicated that FOMO mediates depression and anxiety by a cascade process where PSMU mediates social comparison. The tendency shows that people with a high level of FOMO can initially spend more time on social media to keep up with others, which further increases the comparison between them, causing more emotional misery. This causal chain is consistent with the self-determination theory that assumes that the lack of relatedness and competence needs may lead to maladaptive coping mechanisms and poor well-being (Deci & Ryan, 2010). The results indicate that FOMO is an expression of the unfulfilled psychological needs, which are behaviorally expressed in overconsumption of media and cognitively in the process of never-ending comparisons.

The results can be applied significantly to the Pakistani context where the empirical studies on FOMO and PSMU are scarce. The large explanatory value of the models suggests that FOMO, problematic social media use, and social comparison explain a significant percentage of changes in depression and anxiety as a group. This shows the practical and

clinical importance of these constructs and the necessity to have culturally sensitive intervention strategies to enhance healthier digital habits.

Conclusion

The purpose of this research was to take a closer look at the correlations between fear of missing out (FOMO), problematic social media use (PSMU), social comparison, and psychological health, and the specific values of depression and anxiety in social media users in Pakistan. The results are convincing proof that FOMO is a key factor in defining dysfunctional digital habits and poor psychological well-being. In all the analyses, FOMO proved to be an effective predictor of problematic use of the social media, social comparison, depression, and anxiety, which makes it relevant as a critical psychological vulnerability in the digital generation. The findings also established that problematic use of social media and social comparison are major causes of psychological distress. Both excessive and compulsive use of social media were linked to higher rates of depression and anxiety and problems with regular social comparison exacerbated poor emotional conditions. Notably, the mediation analyses showed that PSMU and social comparison mediate the correlation between FOMO and mental health outcomes partially and sequentially. These results suggest that FOMO has both direct and indirect effects on depression and anxiety because of the augmented use of social media and comparative assessment of the lives of others.

Through the combination of theoretical framing in the theory of uses and gratifications, the theory of self-determination, and the theory of social comparison, this research contributes to the body of knowledge of psychological mechanisms that drive problematic social media use. The findings indicate that preoccupation with unmet psychological needs and fears of social exclusion are the driving forces behind excesses of media use and comparison that subsequently ruin emotional health. Through this, the current research also contributes to the current body of literature by offering empirical data in a non-Western setting, which is a significant gap in the literature on FOMO and mental health. Altogether, the results emphasize the need to target FOMO-related cognitions, problematic social media behaviors, and social comparison tendencies in the

attempt to advance psychological welfare. The interventions that will contribute to the improvement of healthier digital behavior, improvement of self-concept clarity, and a diminished reliance on online validation can be especially helpful in reducing the effects of depression and anxiety among social media users. As social media will become more and more part of daily existence, these psychological processes need to be understood and addressed to help with mental health in modern digital societies.

Limitations & Recommendation

The sample size was small, non-randomly selected through an online survey due to time limitations. And the overall work is generalized other than using a specific social media platform for research, e.g., Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, Twitter, and so on. Further studies can be held on a specific social media platform and in a specific region. Etc.

Contribution

Tayyeb Ramazan conceptualized the study and developed the introduction and research framework. He also contributed to the data analysis and interpretation of results. Sundus Rafi conducted the literature review and synthesized prior research relevant to the study topic. Muhammad Farrukh was responsible for designed the research methodology and applied the analytical procedures used in the study. Nadeem Idris was responsible for data collection and contributed to the conclusion by summarizing key findings and implications of the research. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

REFERENCES

- Alkis, Y., Kadirhan, Z., & Sat, M. (2017). Development and validation of Social Media Disorder Scale. *Psychiatry Research*, 248, 92-99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2016.12.045>
- Ali, S., & Hassan, A. A. U. (2016). Blasphemous Video and Banning of YouTube in Pakistan: Exploring Perception of University and Madaris Students in the Mirror of Uses and Gratification Analysis. *Peshawar Islamicus*, 7(2), 37-46.
- Alt, D. (2019). College students' academic motivation, media engagement and fear of missing out. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 49, 111-119. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2019.02.020>
- Alutaybi, A., & Ali, M. (2020). Fear of missing out and need to belong in social networking sites. *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 30(3), 1-15.
- Andreassen, C. S., Torsheim, T., Brunborg, G. S., & Pallesen, S. (2021). Development of a Facebook addiction scale. *Psychological Reports*, 110(2), 501-517.
- Bartholomew, K., & Horowitz, L. M. (2019). Attachment styles among young adults. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 61(2), 226-244.
- Billieux, J., Maurage, P., Lopez-Fernandez, O., Kuss, D. J., & Griffiths, M. D. (2015). Can disordered mobile phone use be considered a behavioral addiction? *Current Addiction Reports*, 2(2), 156-162.
- Blachnio, A., Przepiórka, A., & Rudnicka, P. (2016). Narcissism and self-esteem as predictors of Facebook addiction. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 90, 296-301.
- Blumler, J. G., Katz, E., & McQuail, D. (2022). *The uses of mass communications: Current perspectives on gratifications research*. Sage Publications.
- Butt, T. Hassan, A. A. U. (2024). Fake News Sharing on Social Media and News Verification Behavior: A Study During Covid-19. *Research Journal of Media and Communication*. 1(1), 1-16
- Buunk, B. P., & Gibbons, F. X. (2007). Social comparison orientation. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(1), 129-142.
- Cochran, W. G. (1977). *Sampling techniques* (3rd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2010). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.

- Elhai, J. D., & Montag, C. (2020). The relationship between fear of missing out and smartphone use disorder. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 36, 27-31.
- Elhai, J. D., & Weeks, J. W. (2018). Cognitive and affective mechanisms of problematic smartphone use. *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, 59, 45-54.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.janxdis.2018.08.002>
- Elhai, J. D., Levine, J. C., Dvorak, R. D., & Hall, B. J. (2018). Fear of missing out, need for touch, anxiety and depression are related to problematic smartphone use. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 63, 509-516.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2016.05.079>
- Farrukh, M., Hassan, A., & Ramazan, T. (2023). Unraveling virtual threads: The impact of social media engagement on family dynamics and Real-Life relationships. *Research Journal for Societal Issues*, 5(3), 328-344.
- Festinger, L. (1954). A theory of social comparison processes. *Human Relations*, 7(2), 117-140.
- Gibbons, F. X., & Buunk, B. P. (1999). Individual differences in social comparison. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 76(1), 129-142.
- Hassan, A. A. U., Ramazan, T., & Baloch, R. B. (2023). Social Disclosure Behavior: Investigating Fake News Sharing on social media and News Verification Amidst the Covid-19. *Media and Communication Review*, 3(2), 41-57.
<https://doi.org/10.32350/mcr.32.03>
- Hassan, A. A. U., Javed, Z., Fazal, M., & Arshad, A. (2022). Children's Rights through the Eye of the Pakistani Press: An Analysis of Print Media. *Media Literacy and Academic Research*, 5(1), 216-229.
- Johnson, R. B., & Christensen, L. (2019). *Educational research: Quantitative, qualitative, and mixed approaches* (6th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Karapanos, E., Teixeira, P., & Gouveia, R. (2016). Need fulfillment and social media fatigue. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 55, 888-895.
- Keel, S., et al. (2020). Social media use and depressive symptoms. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 273, 88-96.
- Kuss, D. J., & Griffiths, M. D. (2017). Social networking sites and addiction. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(3), 311.
- Kwon, M., & Yang, S. (2013). The relationship between smartphone addiction and problematic social media use. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(4), 1449-1454.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.01.022>
- Lariscy, R. W., Avery, E. J., Sweetser, K. D., & Howes, P. (2011). An examination of the role of online social media in journalists' source mix. *Public Relations Review*, 37(3), 293-295.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pubrev.2011.02.011>
- Lin, S., Liu, D., Niu, G., & Longobardi, C. (2022). Social support as a mediator between problematic social media use and mental health. *Current Psychology*.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-02818-5>
- Lovibond, P. F., & Lovibond, S. H. (1983). The structure of negative emotional states: Comparison of the Depression Anxiety Stress Scales (DASS) with the Beck Depression and Anxiety Inventories. *Behaviour Research and Therapy*, 33(3), 335-343.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967\(94\)00075-U](https://doi.org/10.1016/0005-7967(94)00075-U)
- Mannion, A., & Nolan, S. (2020). Fear of missing out and social media dependency: The role of smartphone accessibility. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions*, 9(3), 733-742.
<https://doi.org/10.1556/2006.2020.00060>
- Farrukh, M., Rizvi, W. R., & Ameen, M. (2025). Impact of virtual selves on familial cohesion and amity. *Journal of Media & Communication*, 2022(03), 115-128.
- Nahas, A. R. F., Elkalimi, R., & Hadi, A. A. (2019). Depression among health sciences students. *BMC Medical Education*, 19, 1-8.
- Osman, A., et al. (2017). Internet addiction and depression among Malaysian students. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 28, 103-108.
- Park, C. S. (2023). The role of individual differences in problematic social media use: A uses and gratifications perspective. *Computers in Human*

- Behavior*, 139, 107–118.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2022.107518>
- Primack, B. A., Shensa, A., Sidani, J. E., Whaite, E. O., Lin, L. Y., Rosen, D., Colditz, J. B., Radovic, A., & Miller, E. (2017). Social media use and perceived social isolation among young adults in the U.S. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 53(1), 1–8.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2017.01.010>
- Przybylski, A. K., Murayama, K., DeHaan, C. R., & Gladwell, V. (2013). Motivational, emotional, and behavioral correlates of fear of missing out. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(4), 1841–1848.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.02.014>
- Reer, F., Tang, W. Y., & Quandt, T. (2019). Psychosocial well-being and social media use. *New Media & Society*, 21(2), 1–20.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). *Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness*. Guilford Press.
- Sagioglou, C., & Greitemeyer, T. (2014). Facebook's emotional consequences: Why Facebook causes a decrease in mood and why people still use it. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 35, 359–363.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2014.03.003>
- Salkind, N. J. (2010). *Encyclopedia of research design*. Sage Publications.
<https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412961288>
- Setia, M. S. (2016). Methodology series module 3: Cross-sectional studies. *Indian Journal of Dermatology*, 61(3), 261–264.
<https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5154.182410>
- Smith, R. H., & Kim, S. H. (2007). Comprehending envy. *Psychological Bulletin*, 133(1), 46–64.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.133.1.46>
- Steers, M. N., & Acitelli, L. K. (2014). I get by with a little help from my friends: The role of social support in fear of missing out. *Journal of Social and Personal Relationships*, 31(8), 1014–1034.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0265407514537728>
- Twenge, J. M., & Campbell, W. K. (2018). Associations between screen time and lower psychological well-being among children and adolescents. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, 12, 271–283.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2018.10.003>
- Van Rooij, A. J., Ferguson, C. J., Van de Mheen, D., & Schoenmakers, T. M. (2018). Time to abandon internet addiction? Predicting problematic internet, game, and social media use. *Journal of Behavioral Addictions*, 7(2), 316–326.
<https://doi.org/10.1556/2006.7.2018.35>
- Wang, X., & Cheng, Z. (2020). Cross-sectional studies: Strengths, weaknesses, and recommendations. *Chest*, 158(1), S65–S71.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chest.2020.03.012>
- Whiting, A., & Williams, D. (2013). Why people use social media: A uses and gratifications approach. *Qualitative Market Research*, 16(4), 362–369.
- Williams, D., Stewart, J., & Slack, R. (2012). Social media as a communication tool: A case study of its use in global interaction. *Journal of Communication Management*, 16(3), 256–273.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/13632541211245764>
- Wolniewicz, C. A., & Elhai, J. D. (2021). Fear of missing out and mental health outcomes: A mediated model. *Psychiatry Research*, 296, 113–118.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2020.113743>